
INDIA'S BITTER SUGAR POLICY: PRODUCTION, EXPORT, SUBSIDY, AND OTHER DISTORTIONS

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Abstract

While sugar is widely and progressively highly consumed worldwide, sugar production and exports are highly concentrated among a few countries. This invites many market distortions and demand-supply gaps. India, being the largest producer and the third-largest exporter, creates a lot more distortions than other major producers. Two main sources of volatility are India's production subsidies and export subsidies. These subsidies violate WTO principles of fair trade and increase volatility for other countries too. In addition, sugar is a disaster crop for India as it gets a high premium of subsidies and therefore crowds out other crops, causes resource diversion and immense groundwater depletion, and harbingers a public health crisis in the form of obesity and life-style diseases. We explore the dynamics of the world sugar market, the sources of all the above distortions and adverse effects of the sugar industry, and explore remedial courses, while keeping in mind the political realities.

Keywords: Sugar, Subsidies, Exports, Trade Distortion, Agricultural Policy.

JEL CLASSIFICATION Q13, Q17, Q18

Worldwide, about 110 countries produce sugar; however, only 10 countries account for about 70% of that production. The international sugar consumption has been phenomenal over the last two decades. It has increased from 123.454 million tones to 172.441 million tones, with a compounded annual growth rate of 2.01% in the period between 2001 to 2018 (Heilmann et al., 2018; International Sugar Organization, 2019). Though this growth decelerated and the CAGR between 2010 to 2018 was 0.84% only. The major drivers affecting the demand growth in sugar consumption are attributed to population growth coupled with increased per capita incomes, increased price of sugar and alternative sweeteners, diversified usage of sugar for cleaner fuels and ethanol blending of automobile fuels, and health concerns (International Sugar Organization, 2019).

In 2019, the world recorded a shortfall of supply as compared to demand by 1.169 million tones. A major concern in the global scenario was the decline in both consumption and production of sugar in 2019. This is for the first time since 2011. In 2019, the global sugar production was 169.569 million tones, down from 178.714 million tones (Xia, 2020). Similarly, sugar consumption declined to 170.738 million tones, this is down by 1.229 million tones as compared to 2018. The volume of global sugar trade in 2019 also declined to 57.74 million tones, a reduction of 4.43 million tones from 2018 and 7.8 million tones from 2017. The global sugar stock in 2019 also declined by 1.170 million tones to 110.765 million tones (International Sugar Organization, 2019).

While the sugar market worldwide remained either volatile or in some stage of decline, the Indian sugar production increased due to a host of factors and added to the volatility pressure on the world sugar markets. Such volatility in the sugar sector in the world economy is concerning and requires a deeper analysis, particularly with reference to the major source of this volatility, i.e., Indian sugar subsidies on production and exports. In this paper, we analyze the case of Indian sugar market dynamics. Rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 highlights the situation of world sugar production, consumption, and trade. Section 3 looks at the Indian sugar production, contribution from states, and the political economy driven domestic sugar dynamics of India from an agricultural policy point of view. Section 4 explores the problems caused by the Indian sugar industry from the international trade perspective, particularly in the face of covid-19 pandemic and the rising export subsidies. Section 5 concludes with summarizing our core argument.

2. WORLD SUGAR DYNAMICS

Sugar is among the most widely traded edible commercial crops worldwide. It is also among those few edible crops that can be stored for some duration and released selectively with the demand surge or price surge. While one may think of this feature of sugar as a market smoothening feature, it adds to the overall market volatility mainly owing to motivated government interventions. While many species and condiments affect the countries because of price volatility, sugar is particularly important and politically sensitive due to its derived demand. Any volatility in sugar production or prices thereby, deeply affects the world of celebrations and festivals. Therefore, sugar leads to certain political ramifications also. While sugar can be produced from a wide range of crops, we do not make that source distinction in noting the overall production, consumption, and trade data. As per Table 1, India was the largest sugar producer worldwide in 2019. However, owing to large domestic demand and logistical inefficiencies, India exports far lesser amounts of sugar than Brazil and Thailand (Table 1). However, based on 2006-2015 numbers of production and trade, Sheetal *et al.* (2020) find high comparative advantage for sugar with the EU, US, Guatemala, Mexico, Thailand, China, and India.

Table 1: Top 10 of Sugar - Production and Export (2019)

Rank	10 Largest Producers	In million metric tonnes	Rank	10 Largest Exporters	In million metric tonnes
1	India	29.66	1	Brazil	25.51
2	Brazil	29.17	2	Thailand	18.11
3	EU-28	16.65	3	India	16.20
4	Thailand	14.05	4	Australia	10.55
5	China	10.57	5	Mexico	10.24
6	USA	7.22	6	Guatemala	6.95
7	Russia	7.20	7	South Africa	5.95
8	Mexico	6.18	8	Eswatini	5.35
9	Pakistan	5.33	9	Cuba	4.09
10	Australia	4.25	10	Pakistan	3.19

Source: International Sugar Organization (<https://www.isosugar.org/sugarsector/sugar>)

While the production and export of sugar is detailed in Table 1 above, the total sugar production over the past decade is shown in figure 1. The total production peaked in 2018 at 194.5 million metric tones and is expected to remain higher than the long-term trend in the coming year also despite the global disruptions caused by the pandemic. Compared to the long-term production, the long-term consumption worldwide, as shown in figure 2, has been much more consistent at around 170 million metric tones per annum. It is obvious that given the production volatility and a near constant demand, there would be consumption smoothing over time. This is where a lot of scope of storage, exports, and export subsidies emanate. It is further observed that given the sensitive nature of the commodity and scope of demand-supply gaps, there is ample government intervention across the globe. The cycles of over-production, low prices, huge inventories build-up, and demand gluts occur regularly, adding to the natural crop volatility.

Figure 1: Total Sugar Production Worldwide From 2009 to 2022

Source: Statista and U.S.Department of Agriculture: USDA Foreign Agriculture Service

Figure 2: Total Sugar Consumption Worldwide, 2009-10 to 2020-21

Source: Statista and U.S.Department of Agriculture: USDA Foreign Agriculture Service

The contribution of sugar has increased in the agricultural GDP of India from 5% (1990-91) to 10% (2010-11). India has a total of 716 sugar mills. Out of which, 513 sugar mills are fully operational. The plant size of the sugar mills varies from 2500 Tons of Cane per Day (TCD) to 5000 TCD, with many big mills expanding upto 15000 TCD (Solomon, 2016). In 2015-2016, India was the fourth largest exporter of sugar, contributing 4.5% of the global exports in sugar. Figure 4 shows the total export volume of sugar across India from 2014 to 2019 (in tons).

Figure 4: Total Sugar Export Volume by India, 2014 to 2019

Source: Statista and Department of Commerce (India)

The sugar factories in India are now getting upgraded into “Sugar-Agro-Complexes”. As mentioned earlier, the National Biofuel Policy of the Government of India aims to increase the proportion of ethanol in automobile fuel up to 20% by 2025. This diversification has increased the role of sugar plants beyond mere sugar manufacturing and processing. It is playing an important role in clean fuel movement (Vikash et al., 2018). They have diversified from producing only raw sugar to producing agro-chemical, bioelectricity, bioethanol, bio manure, and similar derived products. The generation of electricity from bagasse has become common in the sugar industry. The sector is self-sufficient in clean energy production and generates exportable surpluses through co-generation (Smouse et al., 1998). The bagasse is also getting used in the Indian paper industry, as a raw material and substitute for wood pulp, making the industry more sustainable. In addition, Molasses has become an important feedstock for

the distilleries, which plays an important role in producing ethanol (Kumar, 2019; Meghana and Shastri, 2020; Setiati et al., 2021).

In India, three-fourth of the entire sugar consumption comes from bulk consumers such as bakeries, candies, ice-cream manufacturers, soft-drink manufacturers and sweet makers. The industrial consumption of sugar is growing due to increased demand in the food processing industry. The by-products of sugar such as jaggery and khandsari (brown sugar) are majorly consumed in rural India (Priyanka et al., 2016). The sugar and related sweetening products consumption is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Consumption of Sugar in India, 2015-2020

Source: Statista and Department of Commerce (India)

In India, sugarcane is cultivated on an area of 5 million hectares (2016-2017). The area of sugar cultivation can be classified into two categories depending on the climatic conditions, i.e., tropical and subtropical. Tropical region covers the northern part (along with the Gangetic part) and the subtropical region covers the southern part of the country. Bihar, Haryana, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand fall under tropical regions; whereas, the states of Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu fall under sub-tropical regions. Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra contribute 65% of the total area in which sugarcane cultivation is done (Upreti and Singh, 2017; NSO-MOSPI, 2014, 2020).

The mean cane productivity of sugarcane in subtropical regions (60 tones per hectare) is lower than that of the mean cane productivity of sugarcane in tropical regions (80 tones per hectare). This is because the tropical-northern part of the country receives favourable climatic conditions with well distributed even sunshine across the year. In sub-tropical regions, erratic rains adversely affect the sugarcane crop (Solomon, 2016). The lower productivity in the subtropical zone is attributed to the comparatively unfavorable climatic conditions as well as water table conditions in this region as compared to tropical regions. This adverse climatic condition as well as water table conditions also impacts the sugar recovery. The sugar recovery in various states of India varies around 9% to 11%, averaging around 10%. However, the potential is 11% in subtropical regions and 13% in tropical regions. The recovery rate in India is below its counterpart such as Brazil (Roy and Chandra, 2018; Sonkar et al., 2020). However, despite the apparent importance of sugar to India, the sugar sector in India faces stiff challenges in many aspects.

4. ISSUES IN THE INDIAN SUGAR INDUSTRY

Apart from the widening gap of productivity between tropical and subtropical regions in India, the sugar industry faces issues due to financial, cyclical, and ecological factors. Sugarcane production is labour intensive and has a high gestation period. In India, the cost of cultivation for sugarcane varies from Rs.70,000 per hectare to Rs.180,000 per hectare (in 2019 USD terms, it varies from \$943 per hectare to \$2,423 per hectare). Also, the increasing cost of fertilizer further increases its woes. Other factors which affect the cost structure of the sugarcane industry is the cyclical nature of sugarcanes (Gupta, 2012; Javalagi and Bhushi, 2014; Kumar, 2019). Unlike Brazil, sugarcane cultivation in India is not synchronized with the demand scenario of the sugar sector. Post the period of bumper harvests, owing to reduced crushing time (with improvement of technology), the manufacturing set-up is heavily underutilized, which affects the cost structure of the domestic firms adversely making them less competitive in the international markets. They are forced to sell the surplus production domestically. Hence, after every year of surplus production, the domestic production falls (Praveen and Samsai, 2014; Das and Dhancholia, 2016). The revenue of sugar companies falls and the farmer payments get reduced. This impacts the morale of farmers adversely and many times motivates them to migrate to other cash crops.

Other factors which impact the productivity of sugar sector are the size of sugar mills and farms, i.e., the scalability of operations. More than 2/3rd of sugarcane cultivation is done within a landholding of less than 1.0 Hectare of land. With small landholdings, innovative agriculture methods cannot be implemented. Most of the sugar mills are operating at a capacity in the range of 2500-3000 TCD with a small proportion of mills working at a capacity of 5000 TCD to 7500 TCD. The smaller size of the sugar

mills inhibits the firms from taking advantage of economies of scale (Meek and Khadse, 2020). One may anticipate that the mills may consolidate into larger size firms eventually to achieve the economies of scale, or some mills would leave the market, allowing remaining mills to become large in size. However, Sheetal *et al.* (2020) find that the government holds the role of the mediating bargaining entity between the sugarcane growers and the sugar mills, which gives rise to significant entry and exit barriers and affects sectoral competitiveness negatively. This is a strong argument against the politically motivated government interventions and urges for free market principle-based reforms. However, owing to political economy factors, such possibilities do not arise.

Another matter of concern for the sugar mills is the ecological factors. With decades of sugarcane farming, the content of soil carbon and organic carbon has depleted with time. Monocropping has led to depletion of soil micronutrients and fertility (Ghayal *et al.*, 2011; Daulta *et al.*, 2014; Lee *et al.*, 2020; Tortorella *et al.*, 2020). Sugarcane is a high-water intensity crop. In India, it requires, on an average, 20 megalitres of water per hectare. This requirement is met through irrigation and rainfall. During the period of weaker monsoon, the crop has to become over dependent on irrigation and exploitation of existing natural water resources crowds out the usage of water resources from other crops. The water table in the sugarcane producing regions has depleted at an alarming rate.

Biotic stresses like alkalinity, salinity, drought, and water logging adversely also affects the sugarcane production. Water logging during monsoons is a major hurdle for sugarcane production (Souza *et al.*, 2017). In India, around 3 Lakh Hectares of sugarcane cultivated area are drought prone, thereby posing a threat of yield reduction by 30%-70% (Vasantha *et al.*, 2005). Also, around 7 lakhs to 8 lakhs hectare of land faces a threat of floods. The threat is more prominent in the Gangetic belt states of India as well as in Odisha and Andhra Pradesh. Water-logging has an adverse impact on various stages of sugarcane crop such as crop germination, establishment, tillering and growth (Gomathi *et al.*, 2015; Solomon, 2016).

4.1 COVID-19 AND SUGAR INDUSTRY

Due to Covid-19 pandemic and resulting lockdown, sugar production as well as its derivatives like ethanol have faced disruption. Indian Sugar Mills Association estimated that approximately Rs. 70,000 Crore is stuck in sugar mills. Also, the demand for ethanol dipped due to a fall in automobile fuel consumption (Ali and Khan, 2020). The pandemic has severely impacted the financial health of sugar mills and this led to delay in their payments to farmers. The pandemic also created disruptions in sulphur, phosphoric acid, lime, packaging bags and labour. However, sugar mills

continued to run during the Covid period as Government of India has categorized this sector under Essential Commodity Act, 1955.

The Pandemic has affected the demand side also. Due to lockdown, demand for ethanol fuel declined, whereas demand from the food and drinks industry (aerated and non-aerated beverages, sweets, restaurants and hotels) also reduced. Due to demand and supply side shocks, the global sugar prices declined, thereby making exports to outside countries unattractive. According to ISMA, this has created an additional stock of 10-12 million in the country (Solomon et al., 2020).

4.2 SUGARCANE PRICING AND EXPORT SUBSIDY IN INDIA

Despite environmental consequences of sugarcane crop, the policymakers find it difficult to take any remedial actions due to political sensitivity of sugar. As the sector employs 7.5% of the rural population with high concentration in select regional pockets, governments always tread caution in policy making related to the sugar sector. In 2009, the "Fair and Remunerative Price" (FRP from here onwards) replaced the Statutory Minimum Price of sugarcane. The cane price is decided by the central government based on the recommendations from the Commission for Agriculture Costs and Prices, State Governments and Sugar Mills Associations. Under the FRP system, the farmers will not have to wait for the sugar mills to declare profits till the end of the season. This system has insulated the farmer's risk of receiving payment of their crop from the fluctuations of the sugar mills' profit. This system links their profits to the recovery rate of sugar. The farmer is paid a premium which is payable to the farmers for a higher level of recovery of sugar from the sugarcane (Shroff and Kajale, 2014).

As sugar is a politically sensitive sector, many states like Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Punjab, Haryana announce state specific State Advised Prices. These prices are generally much higher (30%) than the prices under the FRP system (Reddy, 2011). This creates a price distortion in the system. Due to this reason, farmers tend to overproduce sugar in India, thereby creating a supply glut and adversely affecting the price of sugarcane. As supply of sugarcane increases, the prices of sugar in India fall. In order to facilitate the sugar mill owners to sell their inventory and control the price fall in the domestic markets (due to oversupply), the Government of India announced subsidies on exports violating the rules of WTO.

In 2014, the Government of India announced an export subsidy of Rs.4000 per tone, owing to huge domestic stockpiling of sugar stock for the fifth consecutive year. This was due to bumper crop of sugar canes, low prices in domestic and international markets. It was a hike over the previous subsidy package of Rs. 3300 per tone. At the time of this subsidy (in the third quarter of 2014), the global benchmark index of sugar

i.e., New York raw sugar futures were trading near a more than four-year low (India Trade Portal, 2014).

The subsidy was aimed at enabling the domestic sugar manufacturers to export raw sugar to the standalone refineries in African and other Asian countries. This export subsidy was given with the hope to improve the price competitiveness of domestic sugar manufacturers in the international markets.

In the subsequent years, this subsidy was increased to Rs. 6000 per tone to support the domestic sugar manufacturers. However, in the second half of 2021, the Government of India decided to reduce the subsidy of sugar to Rs. 4000 per tone, which would be applied on all the consignments after May 20, 2021 (Mint, 2021). The subsidy is reduced due to increase in global sugar prices owing to drought in the world's largest producer, Brazil and recovery from global lockdown. This reduction of subsidy is a welcome move as India's sugar subsidy came under the scanner of WTO. The Indian sugar subsidies thus far have violated the letter of the WTO laws as well as the spirit of free market with constant inefficiency induced distortions.

During the country's trade policy review by the WTO in the first half of 2021, countries like the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, and Brazil complained that India's sugar subsidy is responsible for depressing the global sugar prices by 25%. Also, they criticized India for lack of disclosure with regards to providing subsidies in the sugar sector. They raised a question as to why India has not submitted its agri-subsidies (Table ES:1) notification to the Committee on Agriculture since 2009. In the Trade Policy Review of India-2021, the WTO stressed the introduction of reforms in the sugar sector to make the sector competitive along with self-sustainable and subsequent removal of subsidies in this sector, so that a fair-trade environment can be facilitated (Mishra,2021).

Moreover, apart from the compliance to the fair-trade practices, another ethical issue arises out of the fact that a third of Indian sugar is bought by the soft drink makers. Therefore, the tax money is funding a health crisis in the form of aerated beverages, further accentuating the public health havoc of malnutrition as well as obesity. Hence, India should bring reforms in the sugar sector to reduce the dependence of this sector on subsidies. Also, more and more focus should be devoted to reduce the cyclicity of the sector and draft policies which will help sugar mills to diversify them in to Sugar agro-complexes and produce agro-chemical, bioelectricity, bioethanol, bio manure

5. CONCLUSION

While sugar is a socially, politically, and economically important crop for the whole world, the concentration of production and export to a few countries invites a lot of market distortions. India, being the largest producer and the third-largest exporter, creates a lot more distortions. The volatility originates from India's production subsidies as well as export subsidies. Because of these subsidies, two types of problems emerge. One, the domestic crowding out of other crops, resource diversion, groundwater depletion, obesity and related ailments, and regional growth imbalances appear. Two, when India exports its surplus sugar stocks, it distorts prices for others, creates volatility, and violates WTO principles of fair-trade practices also. While any short-term solution is difficult owing to the political realities and complex nature of the sugar industry, it would be desirable to diversify the crop basket over time to promote usage of molasses and other derivatives from the sugar mills, restrict sugar usage by public awareness campaigns, and reduce the water footprint of sugar by restricting the sugar production of select water surplus subtropical regions only.

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